

Wesleyanism

By Tasi Perkins, Georgetown University

Entry tags: Religious Group, Wesleyanism, Methodism

The Methodist/Wesleyan denomination can be said to have commenced in 1738 when John Wesley, an Anglican pastor, had an experience of the Holy Spirit on the road to Aldersgate in the outskirts of London. He wrote in his Journal, following the teachings of Martin Luther on righteousness that, "I felt my heart strangely warmed. I felt I did trust in Christ, Christ alone, for salvation; and an assurance was given me that He had taken away my sins, even mine, and saved me from the law of sin and death." One of the distinctive features of Methodism/Wesleyanism is what has become referred to as its "quadrilateral," the four sources of ecclesiastical authority. These consist of scripture, tradition, experience, and reason. This supplements the Anglican threefold sources, which consist of scripture, tradition, and reason. To the traditional Reformation doctrines of salvation by faith alone (*sola fide*) and justification by faith, and antinomianism, John Wesley added certain maxims that distinguished his movement from the larger Reformation tradition. Acutely among them was his notion of perfection in love in the earthly life. This notion is rooted in 1 John:1 12, 17, Hebrews 12:1f., and Matthew 5:48. Christians are to be perfect as their heavenly father is, especially in love. Additionally, Wesley emphasized a doctrine known as "Arminianism" (named for the Dutch theologian Jacobus Arminius), a rebuke to the Calvinist notion of predestination. Additionally, he stressed the "means of grace" that include of piety, mercy, as well as social and communal practices. With Calvin, Wesley emphasized the "real presence" of Christ in the Eucharistic elements; against Calvin he prescribed an open Communion—even the unbaptized are welcome at the Table of the Lord (he referred to Communion as a potential "converting ordinance." Another chief ordinance is Holy Baptism, performed either in childhood or in adulthood. The United Methodist Book of Worship contends, "The Baptismal Covenant is God's word to us, proclaiming our adoption by grace, and our word to God, promising our response of faith and love." Wesley also borrowed the concepts of prevenient grace, original righteousness, and sanctification from other Christian traditions. Wesley's closest associates were his brother Charles (primarily known for his proficient hymnody) and George Whitefield (himself a Calvinist who believed in predestination), as well as his mother, Susannah who was his foremost spiritual consort. Methodism/Wesleyanism gave birth to the Holiness Movement, which in turn gave birth to Pentecostalism. The Church of Jesus Christ, Latter Day Saints, was formed by a former Methodist. Methodist/Wesleyan denominations today include the United Methodist Church (primarily in the United States but with a large following in sub-Saharan Africa), the Church of the Nazarene, the British Methodists, the African Methodist Episcopal Church, the African Methodist Episcopal Church, Zion, and merged, united denominations in Canada, Zambia, and Australia. Most denominations have an episcopal, connexional polity - a bishop presides over larger collections of congregations, a superintendent over more local collections, and an ordained elder over individual (or multiple) local churches. Lay participation is encouraged.

Date Range: 1738 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Worldwide Wesleyan/Methodist Populations

Region tags: Asia, Europe, North America, Oceania, Africa, Global, United States, Northern Britain, England, Northeastern United States

"Regions with the most adherents to John Wesley's teachings"

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Randy Maddox: Responsible Grace
- Source 2: Nolan Bailey Harmon: The Encyclopedia of World Methodism
- Source 3: Charles Yrigoyen: T&T Clark Companion to Methodism

Reference: Social Principles of the United Methodist Church 2017-2020. United Methodist Publishing House, 2017. <https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Cn7CDgAAQBAJ>.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G_BGLMk37Xs
- Source 1 Description: Rural roots of Methodism
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xCKzOhUaG94>
- Source 1 Description: An overview of John Wesley's life.
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7b_ODz_jgTs&list=PLbh6TrGK235dkOra-qJwRovKU8jyfczq
- Source 1 Description: Collection of Charles Wesley's hymns
- Source 2 URL: <https://worldmethodistcouncil.org/statistical-information/>
- Source 2 Description: List of Methodist / Wesleyan denominations by total membership
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rgqicv3nRdg>
- Source 1 Description: John Wesley and George Whitefield, two of Methodism's founders (the former who taught freewill, the later predestination).

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.christianity.com/bible/commentary.php?com=wes>
- Source 1 Description: John Wesley's Explanatory Notes on the Bible.
- Source 2 URL: United Methodist Social Principles
- Source 2 Description: <http://ee.umc.org/what-we-believe/social-principles-social-creed>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyans have a strong tradition of evangelization and the group grew exponentially in the United States during the Great Awakening. Additionally, the fastest growing Wesleyan groups are found in the Global South, particularly in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. For the early roots of Methodist evangelism, see https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C_BGLMk37Xs.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyans are largely ecumenical. This is especially seen in the "uniting" churches in Canada, Australia, and Zambia, where Methodists have merged with other mainline Protestant groups. Even the United Methodist Church is the product of the merger of three denominations in the 20th century.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: Wesleyanism as a whole fields no military and is not implicated in intra-traditional violent conflict. However, in the United States the Methodist Episcopal Church split into northern and southern denominations prior to the US Civil War (splitting over the issue of clergy owning slaves); the two did not reunite until the mid-20th century. As a result, Methodists were pitted against one another on the battlefield.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Baptism and confirmation are part of the process of becoming a church member. One is not born a Wesleyan but can become a nominal one through infant baptism. In that rite, sponsors pledge faith on behalf of the infant or child, to be maintained until the baptismal candidate is of sufficient age to adopt that faith formally for herself or himself. This adoption is sealed in the rite of confirmation.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Confirmation is the rite by which someone baptized at birth becomes a full member; adult baptism is also an acceptable means for someone previously unbaptized. In many Wesleyan denominations, there is a rite of membership taken before a congregation.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: John Wesley considered "all the world" to be his "parish" and spent the majority of his ministerial career as an itinerant minister, traveling to the masses to preach and celebrate the sacraments. <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/wesley/journal.vi.iii.v.html>.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: The age for membership can vary; typically a person baptized into a Wesleyan/Methodist denomination as an infant becomes a full member through confirmation in early adolescence.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: As stated above, the rites of confirmation, baptism, and membership are done before a congregation and convey membership therein.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Ministers of the Word are charged with preaching the Good News (gospel, evangel) and to call sinners to repentance. This falls short, however, of direct, sustained proselytism.

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Notes: To the extent that it exists, proselytism involves invitation and witness, not coercion. Consider the end of this overview of John Wesley's life: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UwjD_JbOok.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: People as far-ranging as George W. Bush, Hilary Clinton, Harriet Tubman, William McKinley, James K. Polk, and Rosa Parks have all been prominent American Wesleyans, but the tradition itself has not been in political ascendancy.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 60000000

Notes: Total membership in the World Methodist Council. Estimates range from 50 to 80 million. The largest denomination is the US-based United Methodist Church, which claims 13 million adherents around the world.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 3

Notes: This estimate is rough; it depends on the geographical scope of Wesleyanism (see the map above). In the United States, where the plurality of Wesleyans/Methodists live, the denominations comprised roughly 5.7% of the population in 2016.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The "Wesleyan quadrilateral" suggests that doctrinal authority rests in scripture, tradition, reason, and experience. Written scripture consists (in any language) of the 37 books of the Hebrew Bible (the Greek apocrypha is excluded) and the 29 books of the normative New Testament.

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Notes: Wesley's family emphasized the virtue of memorizing scripture, but this scripture remains primarily written.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Notes: 2 Timothy 3:16-17 states, "All scripture is inspired by God and is useful for teaching, for reproof, for correction, and for training in righteousness, so that everyone who belongs to God may be proficient, equipped for every good work." John Wesley comments on this passage: "The Spirit of God not only once inspired those who wrote it, but continually inspires, supernaturally assists, those that read it with earnest prayer. Hence it is so profitable for doctrine, for instruction of the ignorant, for the reproof or conviction of them that are in error or sin, for the correction or amendment of whatever is amiss, and for instructing or training up the children of God in all righteousness." This is less a doctrine of revelation than it is one of inspiration.

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Scripture is believed to be divinely inspired or "God breathed."

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: Divinely inspired humans are understood to have written the scriptures.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: However, Wesley's explanatory notes on the scriptures take on a quasi-authoritative position

Reference: Wesley, John. "John Wesley's Explanatory Notes". Christianity.com, n.d..
<https://www.christianity.com/bible/commentary.php?com=wes>.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The 39 books of the Hebrew Bible and the 27 books of the New Testament are considered to be the canon of mainline Protestant scripture

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: While Wesley borrowed heavily from Eastern Orthodoxy, the Wesleyan tradition never developed a complex iconography. Many Wesleyan churches have begun to incorporate icons into church decor, but rarely are they objects of reverence or foci of worship.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The traditional Continental Protestant distinction between body, soul, and spirit is affirmed by most Wesleyan traditions.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Believers justified by faith inherit eternal life. They are expected to pursue sanctification (holiness) in this life.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Celebrations of life and resurrection are common, but there is no special rite for preparing a body for such a celebration.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Cemetery burial is traditional, but there is no specific doctrinal prescription for it.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Particular practices among individual Wesleyans vary, but there is no doctrinal prescription for domestic burial

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Notes: Celebrations of life and of the resurrection of Jesus Christ are prescribed in most Wesleyan traditions.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: While not strictly anthropomorphic, the God envisioned by the Reformers shares many properties with humans, who are created in the image of God.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Notes: As with most Christians, John Wesley emphasized that God is transcendent of space and time.

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - Notes: John Wesley found this point to be so obvious that in his explanatory notes on the Bible he does not comment on passages that describe God as good.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Trinitarianism
 - Notes: John Wesley, with historically orthodox Christians, understood God to be one Being in three Persons: Father, Son, and Holy Spirit.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - Notes: The Divine for most Christians is omniscient.
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample

region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 6:6 states, "But whenever you pray, go into your room and shut the door and pray to your Father who is in secret; and your Father who sees in secret will reward you." John Wesley comments on this: "Enter into thy closet – That is, do it with as much secrecy as thou canst."

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: While John Wesley was an Arminian, emphasizing free will, he nonetheless taught divine foreknowledge. His Methodist co-founder, George Whitefield, taught Calvinist predestination. For the relationship between the two, see <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rgqicv3nRdg>.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: God is understood to be omniscient.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: Reward is typically seen as heavenly, but the gift of the Holy Spirit leads to earthly sanctification, holiness, and perfection.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Glossing on 1 John 4:8, John Wesley writes, "God is love – This little sentence brought St. John more sweetness, even in the time he was writing it, than the whole world can bring. God is often styled holy, righteous, wise; but not holiness, righteousness, or wisdom in the abstract, as he is said to be love; intimating that this is his darling, his reigning attribute, the attribute that sheds an amiable glory on all his other perfections."

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley frequently exhorted his followers "to flee from the wrath to come."
<https://www.umcdiscipleship.org/blog/can-we-still-talk-about-part-1-the-wrath-to-come>.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Trinitarianism

Notes: The supreme high god for Wesley is the Holy Trinity.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The age of prophecy is considered to be over, though the preaching of the Word of God is considered a means of grace. Some in the Holiness / Pentecostal traditions, which derive from Wesleyanism, do believe that God actively speaks to and through

sanctified people.

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– No

↳ Through divination practices:
– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– No

↳ Only through monarch
– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

Notes: Wesleyans, like most Christians, believe in the communion of the saints -- i.e. that at the sacrament all Christians past, present, and future, are mystically present, but they do not believe that human spirits are more tangibly present.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

Notes: Angels are widely accepted, but they play no special role in Wesleyan doctrine.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The tradition recognizes "angels and archangels" but does not emphasize them.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyanism teaches adherence to Wesley's rules. Briefly, they consist of doing no harm, doing all the good one can, and attending upon the ordinances of God:

<https://www.umc.org/en/content/the-general-rules-of-the-methodist-church>.

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– No

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Methodism recognizes the Decalogue, which forbids killing. John Wesley expounds on this: "Thou shalt not do any thing hurtful to the health, or life of thy own body, or any other's. This doth not forbid our own necessary defence, or the magistrates putting offenders to death; but it forbids all malice and hatred to any, for he that hateth his brother is a murderer, and all revenge arising therefrom; likewise anger and hurt said or done, or aimed to be done in a passion; of this our Saviour expounds this commandment, Matthew 5:22." He continues by commenting on this verse from Matthew, which forbids unjust anger: "Whosoever shall say, Thou fool – Shall revile, or seriously reproach any man. Our Lord specified three degrees of murder, each liable to a sorer punishment than the other: not indeed from men, but from God."

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Commenting on one of the verses commanding the extermination of other peoples (Deuteronomy 7:24), Wesley simply says that the Israelites squander the blessings of slaughter of their enemy if they are disobedient.

Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: Lust and adultery are generally forbidden.

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Wesley writes, commenting on Matthew 5:27-29, "Thou shalt not commit adultery – And this, as well as the sixth commandment, the scribes and Pharisees interpreted barely of the outward act. Exodus 20:14, 29, 30. If a person as dear as a right eye, or as useful as a right hand, cause thee thus to offend, though but in heart. Perhaps here may be an instance of a kind of transposition which is frequently found in the sacred writings: so that the 29th verse may refer to 27, 28; and the 30th to verse 21, 22. Matthew 5:29,27,28,30,21,22 As if he had said, Part with any thing, however dear to you, or otherwise useful, if you cannot avoid sin while you keep it. Even cut off your right hand, if you are of so passionate a temper, that you cannot otherwise be restrained from hurting your brother. Pull out your eyes, if you can no otherwise be restrained from lusting after women. Matthew 18:8; Mark 9:43."

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Sex outside of the marriage bond is generally frowned upon.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Per the Decalogue, false witness is forbidden: commenting on Matthew 5:37 (<https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=mt+5.34-37&version=NRSV>), John Wesley writes, "in your common discourse, barely affirm or deny."

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Per the Decalogue, God cares about false witness. In the Sermon on the Mount, Jesus declares, "Do not swear at all, either by heaven, for it is the throne of God, or by the earth, for it is his footstool, or by Jerusalem, for it is the city of the great King. And do not swear by your head, for you cannot make one hair white or black" (Matthew 5:34-36)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: The term "Methodist," which was applied to Wesley's followers, applies to the methodical and intentional method that they were to have in following his religious program

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: "Elder" has a special connotation in Methodism -- those who are ordained ministers in the church

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Wesley was particularly insistent that his followers observed "constant communion;" i.e., that they took the Eucharist frequently

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Sacraments are important and are a means of grace through which salvation is attained. Obedience in general is acclaimed, as Wesleyan hymnody articulates:

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iQUmBX17c0c&list=PLS4jQgASCDFFKnsrST9YQVft3DxIbtEyA&index=6)

[v=iQUmBX17c0c&list=PLS4jQgASCDFFKnsrST9YQVft3DxIbtEyA&index=6](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iQUmBX17c0c&list=PLS4jQgASCDFFKnsrST9YQVft3DxIbtEyA&index=6)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: As heirs to Luther's reformation, Wesleyans are evangelicals; however, proselytism is not generally encouraged

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley famously lived his life on a modest salary, setting an example for his followers. Wesleyans have a strong legacy of fighting for social and economic justice.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=11v=2Yo6IsLRNMM&feature=emb_logo; also <http://ee.umc.org/what-we-believe/economic-community>.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The Other is greatly cared about; see John Wesley's notes on Hebrews 13, which states, "Do not neglect to show hospitality to strangers, for by doing that some have entertained angels without knowing it."

Notes: <https://www.christianity.com/bible/commentary.php?com=wes&b=58&c=13>

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: As inheritors of the larger "orthodox" Christian tradition and its seven ecumenical councils, Wesleyans affirm with the words of the Nicene Creed that Christ as Lord "will come again in glory to judge the living and the dead." <https://www.umc.org/en/content/glossary-nicene-creed>.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Jesus Christ is considered to be the ultimate Judge, but there is a role that Satan plays in the infliction of punishment.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The forces of Good and Evil combine in the punishment of sinners.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The punishment of hell is meted out through Satan.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: By advising followers to attend upon the ordinances of God, Wesley encourages pursuit of sanctification and the avoidance of "the wrath to come."

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyans typically believe in eternal reward for those who receive the justification of Christ's righteousness by faith and eternal damnation for those who refuse this gift of grace. However, this belief varies from person to person in day-to-day practice.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Consider this article on the relationship between Wesleyanism and the doctrine of hellfire: <https://goodnewsmag.org/2011/09/how-can-united-methodists-believe-in-hell/>.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: John Wesley was firmly committed to Martin Luther's doctrine of justification by faith, through which one is imbued with Christ's righteousness. This has eternal implications; divine punishment is escatological rather than temporal. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DBDQIOz4K6c>

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: People are justified by faith, not by works; still the lessons of Matthew 25 remain: <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=mt+25%3A31-46&version=NRSV>. Herein lies a major difference between Martin Luther and John Wesley. For Wesley justification is the door through which one enters into the journey of sanctification (holiness) -- good works follow naturally from salvation.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Attending to the means of grace (such as the sacraments) binds adherents together. Consider the "ordinances of God" for John Wesley: The public worship of God, the ministry of the Word, either read or expounded the Supper of the Lord, family and private prayer, searching the Scriptures, and fasting or abstinence.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Justification by faith is a core teaching of the Reformation, to which John Wesley was an heir. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oQUS_nxcWeY.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyans, like most normative Christians, believe in eternal bliss for the saved.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

Notes: Heavenly reward is joy, not sensual pleasure.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: <https://www.ministrymatters.com/all/entry/359/reclaiming-john-wesleys-holistic-salvation>.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: The Wesleyan faith, based in the Biblical witness, teaches the doctrine of resurrection, not reincarnation: <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=1+Corinthians+15%3A12-28&version=NRSV>.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: Resurrection, not reincarnation, is the Wesleyan norm: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QGFtc8QZ64k>.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Notes: There is a strong Wesleyan notion of pacifism: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1_q4ccrMJ2g.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– No

Notes: Though scriptures speak of glad tidings related to peace, there is no formal Wesleyan doctrine stating that temporal peace is a supernatural reward -- it is a gift of grace instead.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– No

Notes: Many Wesleyans involved in agriculture praise God for these blessings.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The experience of grace comforts the justified and leads to the holiness and perfection of sanctification.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– No

Notes: The Bible speaks of such signs of divine favor, but the Wesleyan tradition does not emphasize them.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: Matthew 24:36 states, "But about that day and hour no one knows, neither the angels of heaven, nor the Son, but only the Father." John Wesley comments, "The day of judgment; Knoweth no man - Not while our Lord was on earth. Yet it might be afterward revealed to St. John consistently with this."

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The messiah is coming, for Wesleyans, to consummate the cosmos.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Consumation of the worldly order.

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Worldwide Wesleyan Populations

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The Continental Reformers, to whom John Wesley was an heir, taught that the Kingdom of God is "here but not yet."

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: As the Creed accepted by John Wesley suggests, Christ will come in final victory, and his Kingdom will have no end.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

Notes: While not Millenarianists, Wesleyans do anticipate a future consummation of the created order.

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley looked forward to a safe passage through divine judgment: "I drop into an unchangeable eternity! I want to know one thing,—the way to heaven; how to land safe on that happy shore" <https://www.bartleby.com/209/750.html>.

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Notes: The telos / consummation of humanity is linear and will result in the eternal eschaton.

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley, commenting on Philippians 2:10-11, writes, "That every knee – That divine honour might be paid in every possible manner by every creature. Might bow – Either with love or trembling. Of those in heaven, earth, under the earth – That is, through the whole universe. And every tongue – Even of his enemies. Confess that Jesus Christ is Lord – Jehovah; not now "in the form of a servant," but enthroned in the glory of God the Father."

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: For John Wesley it is God's prerogative to determine who has been justified by faith.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: <https://www.umc.org/en/what-we-believe/basics-of-our-faith/our-social-positions>.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: Like most Christian groups, Wesley's heirs link morality to God's gracious and loving nature.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Faith, hope, and love are considered the chief heavenly virtues

Reference: Wesley, John. "Wesley on Salvation by Faith". 2013,1,19, 1927.

[https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-I7Bf-](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-I7Bf-M8krw&list=PLfXiMMKkjz_DHisrWpS_LD1co7YdmH3Bb&index=2)

[M8krw&list=PLfXiMMKkjz_DHisrWpS_LD1co7YdmH3Bb&index=2.](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-I7Bf-M8krw&list=PLfXiMMKkjz_DHisrWpS_LD1co7YdmH3Bb&index=2)

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - No
 - Notes: Attending to the sacraments is important
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Yes

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: For most Wesleyans, abstinence in singlehood and fidelity in marriage is a requisite.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence in singlehood, fidelity in marriage.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Abstinence in singlehood, fidelity in marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley highly recommended regular fasting (Wednesdays and Fridays), but it is rarely practiced today except during Lent.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: John Wesley did not support the overconsumption of alcohol: <http://www.nodrinking.com/john-wesley-word-to-a-drunkard/>

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Tithing (donating 10% of one's income) is highly encouraged.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– Yes

Notes: Charity in general is encouraged

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Personal prayer is encouraged, and emphasized in the Wesleyan tradition.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: The sacrament of communion, which involves an entire church, is encouraged.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A denomination, or rather a communion of some 80 denominations rooted in the Wesleyan tradition.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: UMCOR (The United Methodist Committee on Relief) is a major benevolent ministry:
<https://www.umcmission.org/umcor>.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Training is available to clergy and laity alike.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Some Wesleyan denominations only ordain males, but access to religious education is available for laity of all sexes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Most Wesleyan sects have a polity that involves bishops, elders, and laypeople (some also include deacons and superintendents). Wesley's "method" involved what he called "connexionalism," the idea of concentric levels of authority that made decisions affecting local congregations and the movement as a whole.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Wesleyan denominations have many commissions and committees that interact with other benevolent societies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Wesleyanism has a strong connection to food pantries, soup kitchens, and feeding ministries.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: Tithes and dues are not typically required, but are emphasized

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Apart from civil taxes, no dues are implemented on Wesleyans.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: John Wesley recognizes the authority of the Hebrew law, but subsumes it under his doctrine of grace. The law is not abolished but rather fulfilled through Jesus Christ, whose righteousness is imposed on believers.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: States with universal conscription do not tend to exempt Wesleyans from military service.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: Most Wesleyans are English-speaking, but there is no sacred language

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The liturgical calendar involves a 3-year lectionary of prescribed Scripture readings (each Sunday, there are lessons from the Hebrew Bible writ large, the Psalms, the Gospels, and the Epistles) and there are ten holidays observed each year (Christmas Day, Epiphany, Baptism of the Lord, Easter Sunday, Ascension Day, Pentecost, Trinity Sunday, Transfiguration Sunday, All Saints' Day, and Christ the King Sunday) as well as a number of fast days such as Ash Wednesday and Good Friday and some regionally observed holidays

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Wesleyanism, Maddox, Randy L.. Responsible Grace. Kingswood Series, 1994.
https://books.google.com/books/about/Responsible_Grace.html?hl=&id=iHYOAAAACAAJ.

Reference: Wesleyanism, Yrigoyen, Charles. T&T Clark Companion to Methodism. A&C Black, 2010.
https://books.google.com/books/about/T_T_Clark_Companion_to_Methodism.html?hl=&id=A6NHNICaNP8C.

Reference: Wesleyanism, Harmon, Nolan Bailey. The Encyclopedia of World Methodism, 1974.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Encyclopedia_of_World_Methodism.html?hl=&id=8b2HSwAACAAJ.

Reference: Wesleyanism, The Encyclopedia of African Methodism, 2019.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Encyclopedia_of_African_Methodism.html?hl=&id=zTU_zQEACAAJ.

Reference: Wesleyanism, González, Justo L.. A History of Christian Thought. Abingdon Press, 2014.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=JrMpAgAAQBAJ>.

Reference: Wesleyanism, Wainwright, Geoffrey. For Our Salvation. Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing, 1997.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=FC6YJ60NjHIC>.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: No, Wesley, John. "John Wesley's Explanatory Notes". Christianity.com, n.d..
<https://www.christianity.com/bible/commentary.php?com=wes>.

Reference: Yes, Wesley, John. "Wesley on Salvation by Faith". 2013,1,19, 1927.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-l7Bf-M8krw&list=PLfXiMMKkjz_DHisrWpS_LD1co7YdmH3Bb&index=2.

Reference: Source 1: Randy Maddox: Responsible Grace, Source 2: Nolan Bailey Harmon: The Encyclopedia of World Methodism, Source 3: Charles Yrigoyen: T&T Clark Companion to Methodism, Social Principles of the United Methodist Church 2017-2020. United Methodist Publishing House, 2017.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=Cn7CDgAAQBAJ>.